

Port of Rotterdam (NL)

This fiche includes maps displaying the location of the sampling points (SPOs) around the port of Rotterdam (NL) with measurements of NO₂ and PM_{2.5} in 2023 (E1a validated data AQ e-Reporting). The tables include additional information on the annual mean concentrations of each SPO with available data (data coverage larger than 75%), distances of the SPOs from the port area, location of the SPO in one of the 8 wind sectors around the port (WS: N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW), population living in the WS within 10 km from the port, and trends of annual mean concentrations (2005-2023) when available. This information has been complemented with the EEA air quality annual maps (1 km x 1 km), covering the whole area around the port and showing in the boxplot the different levels concentrations over the port area compared to the surrounding region, including the weighted area means for the different land cover classes. The presented information is based only on SPOs reported to the EEA, additional SPOs or data may exist at national level.

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Port area and NO₂ air quality SPOs around the port within 5 and 10 km

Port area and PM_{2.5} air quality SPOs around the port within 5, 10 and 20 km

Pozzoli, L., Gressent, A., Soares, J., Colette, A., Monge, S. & González Ortiz, A. (2025). Air quality around ports (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2024/12, version 2, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17416089>).
[ETC HE Report 2024/12: Air quality around ports — Eionet Portal](#)

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NO₂ SPOs in 2023 around the port

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Netherlands	NL00485	Background	51.87	4.36	18.13	-54.20	0.94	SE	35,211
Netherlands	NL00449	Traffic	51.91	4.33	24.40		1.81	E	98,289
Netherlands	NL00495	Background	51.93	4.23	23.52		1.96	N	49,140

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PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the port (Part 1)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Netherlands	NL00488	Background	51.89	4.49	9.36		0.18	E	98,289
Netherlands	NL00487	Traffic	51.89	4.48	9.15		0.32	E	98,289
Netherlands	NL00494	Background	51.92	4.40	8.72		0.78	E	98,289
Netherlands	NL01497	Background	51.93	4.00	8.20		0.83	W	15,415
Netherlands	NL00485	Background	51.87	4.36	8.54		0.94	SE	35,211
Netherlands	NL00418	Background	51.91	4.48	7.75		0.99	E	98,289
Netherlands	NL00496	Industrial	51.98	4.12	9.10		1.53	NW	9,678
Netherlands	NL00449	Traffic	51.91	4.33	7.45		1.81	E	98,289
Netherlands	NL00495	Background	51.93	4.23	8.41		1.96	N	49,140
Netherlands	NL00493	Traffic	51.93	4.46	8.81		2.27	E	98,289

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PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the port (Part 2)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Netherlands	NL00491	Traffic	51.94	4.43	8.90		2.77	E	98,289
Netherlands	NL00450	Traffic	52.06	4.32	7.33		16.88	N	49,140
Netherlands	NL00404	Background	52.08	4.29	6.91		16.96	N	49,140

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Annual mean NO₂ concentrations in 2023

EEA air quality map (1 km x 1 km)

Concentrations over the port area compared to the surrounding region. Coloured dots correspond to weighted area means for different land cover classes in the surrounding region.

- High density residential
- Low density residential
- Industry
- Traffic
- Agricultural areas
- Natural areas

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Annual mean PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2023

EEA air quality map (1 km x 1 km)

Concentrations over the port area compared to the surrounding region. Coloured dots correspond to weighted area means for different land cover classes in the surrounding region.

- High density residential
- Low density residential
- Industry
- Traffic
- Agricultural areas
- Natural areas

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